

Influence of Exposure to Violence on Delinquent Behaviours among Adolescents in Awka Metropolis

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ABSTRACT: The study examined the influence of exposure to violence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design. It was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population comprised of 73,000 adolescents residing in Awka according to 2006 census population. The sample size was 398 respondents drawn from the population using Taro Yamen Formula. The instrument for the study was developed by the researcher titled "Delinquent Behaviours Questionnaire" (DBQ). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronchbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.79 for status delinquent behaviours and 0.68 for property delinquent behaviours. Three hundred and seventy-four (374) duly completed copies of the instrument were retrieved and used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics. The findings from the analysis showed that exposure to violence has a significant influence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis. The study recommends that counselling centers should be established to provide therapy and behavioural modifications for adolescents who are affected by violence exposure. More so, government should formulate and implement policies that reduce youth unemployment, as economic hardship often gives rise to social unrest and delinquency.

KEYWORDS: Exposure to Violence, Delinquent Behaviours and Adolescents

INTRODUCTION

Delinquent behaviour has become increasingly a pervasive social concern, particularly among adolescents, with significant implications for development and for societal well-being. which is likely to pose a great risk for the society in general and cause a bleak future for adolescents in particular. The rising prevalence of delinquent behaviours has attracted considerable scholarly and institutional attention, prompting psychologists, educators, and juvenile justice systems globally to investigate its underlying causes. The conceptualization of delinquency can be traced to 19th-century in England, where youth crime emerged as a significant socio-political issue threatening public order, largely driven by industrialization, urban poverty, and family disintegration (Magarey, 1978). Delinquency encompasses a range of behaviours that violate societal norms or laws, including truancy, aggression, theft, vandalism, substance abuse, and defiance of authority, often associated with social environments characterised by violence and instability. Brindlmayer et al (2022) defined delinquent behaviours as minor or unlawful acts committed by individuals that contravene societal rules. Common forms of delinquent behaviours among adolescents include theft, property damage, physical aggression, gang involvement, sexual offences, substance abuse, burglary, robbery, vandalism, and avoiding school (López et al., 2019). From a psychological perspective, delinquent behavior is often understood as a product of maladjustment, personality, factors, cognitive distortions, and learned behaviours (Gupta & Mahanta, 2021). The age-range of delinquent behaviours varies according to countries. In Western world for instance, delinquent behaviours are often observed among the age-range of 14-15 years. But by the age of 16 and 17, such harmful behaviours become more dangerous and metamorphose into the use of weapons. In African context, the age range consists of individuals under the age of 18.

Delinquent behaviours of adolescents are generally categorized into various types namely: status offences, property offences, person-related offences and substance-related offences. Status offences are behaviours deemed unlawful solely because of the individual's age which include truancy, running away from home, underage drinking, smoking, and violating curfews Sprott, (2012). Property offences encompass crimes against property such as theft, shoplifting, burglary, arson, and vandalism (Sankey, 1999; McKissack, 1974). Person-related offences include assault, bullying, sexual harassment, fighting, and participation in gang violence. Such behaviours reflect poor emotional regulation and exposure to aggressive role models, often through community violence or domestic abuse. Substance-related offences are behaviours that are linked to possession, use, or distribution of illegal substances. The current study focuses on status and property categories of adolescents' delinquent behaviours. In the current study, delinquent behaviours refer to anti-social actions that confronts the offender to societal norms usually committed by teenagers.

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As a matter of fact, the rising of delinquent behaviours among adolescents has elicited societal and scholarly reactions, that calls for an in-depth study on the factors that perpetuate this trend and the parameters required to ameliorate it. Robinson, (2022) posited that evidence of delinquent behaviour is a tremendous problem that is linked with exposure violence. Adolescents who are exposed to violence, directly or indirectly, either as victims or as witnesses, are at increased risk of becoming violent themselves. Finkelhor et al. (2015), with support from the US Department of Justice's Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention, conducted a national survey on exposure to violence by adolescents in which the researchers reported that more than 60% of US children were exposed to some forms of violence in the past year. In the same vein, Nigerian adolescents are gradually subsumed into the violence either as perpetrators, perpetuators or observers. As the adolescents are exposed to violence, there is tendency that the horrific events of shootings, killings, abductions, rape, fighting, just to mention but a few will fill their thoughts, which is likely to lead them into delinquent behaviours and destabilise their future. Adolescence is defined as the span of years between childhood and adulthood, during which individuals are particularly vulnerable to environmental influences that shape their behaviour and life outcomes (Steinberg, 2014). These influences, when negative, often manifest in socially unacceptable and antisocial behaviours, raising concerns about the development of adolescents. Like infancy, adolescence is often characterised as a period of considerable disturbance; as G. Stanley Hall described it, a time of "storm and stress" (Hall, 1904). During the adolescent period, adolescents are subjected to psychological conditions which includes cognitive, emotional and intellectual ability; physical disabilities; carrying weapons; involvement in substance abuse.

Violence exposure constitutes a risk factor that is linked with the emergence and persistence of delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Nigeria. In Awka metropolis, Anambra State, this phenomenon has become increasingly pronounced as adolescents navigate through environments characterised by recurrent violent incidents with homes, schools and the wider community. The proliferation of cult-related conflicts, gang activities, kidnappings, and domestic disputes has created a social climate in which young persons are frequently exposed to violence either as direct victims or as witnesses. Such exposure may contribute to the internalization of aggressive norms and normalization of antisocial behaviours during the early stages of development. Empirical and media reports indicate that Awka has experienced repeated episodes of cult-related violence in recent years. For instance, recurring violent clashes between rival cult groups have resulted in numerous fatalities across different parts of Awka metropolis, including areas around Eke Awka and Okpuno (Obianeri, 2024). In April 2024, alone, reports indicated that a series of cult-related confrontations led to several deaths and heightened insecurity within the city (Eleke, 2024; Ujumadu, 2024). Two individuals suspected of involvement in cult-related activities were reportedly killed in Awka, the capital of Anambra State, during a confrontation between rival groups (Chukwudi, 2023).

Similarly, subsequent incidents in nearby communities within Awka South Local Government Area further emphasise the persistent nature of these clashes, which have continued to cause fatalities and insecurity in the area. (Obianeri, 2024). Such occurrences contribute to an atmosphere of turmoil and instability within the community, where adolescents may be exposed to traumatic experiences that shape their behavioural outcomes. The strategic location of Awka as both a commercial and an educational hub surrounded by higher institutions of learning such as Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University (Igbariam campus), and Anambra State Polytechnic has been linked to increased youth population density including risk of cultism and incessant attacks. In as much as the higher institutions of learning serve as centres of intellectual development, their existence may create an atmosphere where violent peer networks and cult affiliations spread like wildfire, thereby exposing adolescents in surrounding communities to deviant peer influences.

Repeated violence within adolescents' environment can have adverse effect on the development of a healthy personality. Studies have consistently shown that adolescents exposed to community or domestic violence are more likely to exhibit behavioural and emotional problems which include aggression, anxiety, depression, and rule-breaking behaviours (Finkelhor et al, 2015; Margolin and Gordis, 2000). Such exposure can impair emotional regulation and cognitive development, thereby increase the likelihood of delinquent behaviours among adolescents. Additionally, social learning theory on which this study anchors highlights that repeated exposure to violence may lead to antisocial behaviours among young people (Bandura, 1977). The persistent exposure of adolescents to violence in neighborhoods, schools, and public domains not only impairs their psychosocial development but also heightens the risk of adopting delinquent behaviours as a form of coping or learned response. Numerous studies have shown that repeated exposure to violence is often linked to a series of behavioural and psychological problems in adolescents such as aggression, substance abuse and decline in academic performance (Menard et al, 2015; Myers et al, 2018; Lofving-Gupta et al, 2018; Coleman & Farrell, 2021; DiClemente & Richards, 2022; Allwood et al, 2023).

Exposure to violence implies witnessing, being affected by, or being aware of violence of any form or experiencing violence through child abuse and neglect or in a violent incident at home or community. Exposure to violence has been defined by recent scholars from different dimensions, viz: war, civil, family dynamics, community among others (Frontiers, 2021; Huesman et al., 2023; World Mental Health Surveys, 2023). Kuposov et al, (2021) referred to community violence exposure as witnessing of, or victimised by a violent person within one's home, school, or neighbourhood, between individuals who are unrelated, and who may or may not know each other. Huesman et al., (2023) defined exposure to war violence as being exposed to war-related violent events, which may include witnessing violence, living through violent political conflict, or being affected by related stressors. Exposure to civil violence

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is conceptualized as a self-report of having been a civilian in a war zone or region of terror (Bunting, 2023). Exposure to violence in the current study is defined as an individual's direct or indirect experience of violent acts, including being a victim, witnessing incidents, or being aware of violence occurring with their environment. Such exposure may occur at home, in the school, workplace, or broader community. Exposure to violence is an adolescent environmental stressor which includes domestic violence, school-related aggression, community violence, media-induced brutality, intergenerational trauma and peer violence among others. Exposure to violence heightens the risk of poor academic performance, addiction of substance abuse, low employment opportunities in adolescents and might lead them to becoming victims of or perpetrators of violence. Exposure to violence whether inside or outside the home environment is associated with the development of aggression in teenagers. Research has shown that children and adolescents have a wide range of reactions to exposure to violence (Carey, 2012). Some of them are adversely affected or may show only brief and transient reactions. Others may be more affected, showing significant symptoms and emotional vulnerability. Some develop intense anxiety disorders or post-traumatic stress disorder. Given the prevalence of the troubling trend of violence exposure with the rising wave of adolescents' delinquency in Awka metropolis, exposure to violence does not remain a distant social issue but becomes a lived experience that undermines adolescents' academic progress, social adjustment, and respect for authority. Consequently, investigating the influence of violence exposure on delinquent behaviours in Awka is not only timely but also of great significance in order to reduce youth exposure to violence and its behavioural consequences.

Statement of the Problem

The alarming rate of delinquent behaviours of adolescents among adolescents may lead to a bleak future. As a matter of fact, delinquent behaviour is a pervasive challenge in the world today and is a matter of grave concern to psychologists, stakeholders, educationists, juvenile and social planners. A lot of studies have been carried out by experts to ascertain the causes and effects of this worrisome problem which vary across socio-cultural and economic contexts. Empirical evidence suggests that exposure to violence can lead to aggression, truancy, theft, substance abuse, bullying, and other forms of delinquency. However, these studies have not yielded the much-desired results as the issue continues to escalate leading to widespread panic among citizens. There seems to be dearth of sufficient empirical evidence to examine the influence of exposure to violence on delinquent behaviours of adolescents particularly in Awka metropolis. It is this gap that the present study intends to fill. The problem of this study is therefore stated in question form thus: What is the influence of exposure to violence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on Bronfenbrenner's Ecological System Theory developed by Bronfenbrenner (1978) which provides a framework of understanding how individuals and their environments interact. The basic tenet of Bronfenbrenner's ecological system theory is that human development is influenced by various systems, from immediate contexts to broader societal factors which includes microsystem (family, peers, school), mesosystem (interactions between microsystems), exosystem (parental workplaces, neighbourhood environments), macrosystem (cultural and societal norms), and chronosystem (time-based events and transitions). Each subsystem interacts to affect individuals' behaviour either positively or negatively. Bronfenbrenner underscores that children and adolescents may adopt behaviours by interacting with any of the subsystems. The theory therefore provides valuable insights into the adverse effect of exposure to violence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the influence of exposure to violence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours of adolescents in Awka Metropolis.
2. Ascertain the influence of exposure to violence on property delinquent behaviours of adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis?
2. What is the influence of exposure to violence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at .05 level of significance

1. Exposure to violence has no significant influence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.
2. Exposure to violence has no significant influence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

METHODS

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The Population was 73,000 adolescents residing in Awka (source: Population Census Bureau Statistics and Record, 2006). Taro Yamen formula was used to reduce the population to 398 adolescents from Awka

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metropolis with the return rate of 374. Data was collected from the respondents using a self-structured instrument titled “Delinquent Behaviours Questionnaire (DBQ)”. The instrument was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha method. This process yielded a coefficient value of 0.79 for status delinquent behaviours and 0.68 for property delinquent behaviours. The questionnaire was made up of two clusters. Cluster one has seven item statements which elicited information on behaviours considered exclusively illegal due to respondents’ status while cluster two has eight item statements which elicited information on the actions of the respondents that involve destruction of properties. The response format for the instrument was a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA) and Strongly Disagree (SD). They were weighted as follows: SA = 4, A = 3, DA = 2 and SD = 1 point. Out of the 398 copies of the questionnaire administered, 374 copies were correctly completed and retrieved from the respondents. This represents 93.9% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. For the research questions, mean score of above 2.50 was regarded as agreed, while mean score of below 2.50 was regarded as disagreed and the mean average of 2.50 was used for decision making. Any item mean that was 2.50 and above was accepted while any of them that was below 2.50 was rejected.

RESULTS

The data collected were analysed and presented in tables in line with the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study:

Research Question 1: What is the influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	I have been in several physical fights at school since being bullied by a classmate	2.92	1.02	Agree
2.	I have been skipping school frequently to avoid being hurt by rival gang members	2.84	0.93	Agree
3.	I resorted to smoking cigarettes to ease off tension of being beaten up in the neighbourhood	2.84	0.97	Agree
4.	I defy parental authority by refusing to follow household rules after witnessing a violent crime	2.76	1.07	Agree
5.	I am running away from home to seek safety elsewhere because of repeated physical abuse	2.64	1.13	Agree
6.	I have been using social media to threaten others after being cyberbullied myself	2.84	1.05	Agree
7.	I started consuming alcohol at an early stage having grown up in a violent community	3.12	0.95	Agree
	Average Grand Mean	2.85	1.02	

The data in Table 1 presents the influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis. The result of the analysis showed that all the respondents scored above 2.50 in items 1-7. With the average grand mean of 2.85 which is above the criterion weighted mean score of 2.50, it implies that exposure to violence strongly influences status delinquent behaviours of adolescents residing in Awka metropolis.

Table 2: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on influence of exposure to violence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	I break dishes in my family because I was physically abused	2.81	0.98	Agree
2.	Smashing windows has become a coping mechanism after all the shouting I grew up with	2.50	1.03	Agree
3.	I deface the walls with graffiti after I got into fight with a gang member	2.75	0.94	Agree
4.	I started stealing valuables since I got robbed at a gunpoint	3.05	0.86	Agree
5.	I got used to vandalising school properties from the time I fought with a classmate	2.74	1.04	Agree
6.	I steal repeatedly from my classmates' lockers after being bullied	2.41	0.86	Disagree

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7.	I have been setting fires in abandoned buildings after witnessing a fight in my neighbourhood	3.15	0.36	Agree
8.	Stealing is an outlet for me after witnessing so much violence at home	2.66	1.19	Agree
Average Grand Mean		2.76	0.91	

Table 2 shows the analysis of the responses on influence of exposure to violence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis. The mean responses on the various item statements 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7 and 8 are all greater than the critical mean level of 2.50 except item 6 which is below 2.50. This implies that exposure to violence has strong influence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Exposure to violence has no significant influence on status delinquent behaviour among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

Table 3: T-test analysis on the Mean Ratings of Exposure to Violence on Status Delinquent Behaviour among Adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Std. Mean	Error T	P- value
Exposure to violence has no significant influence on status delinquent behaviour among adolescents in Awka Metropolis	374	2.85	0.67	0.034	82.8	.000

The result in Table 3 revealed that the mean was 2.85, standard deviation was 0.67, t value was 82.8, p value was 0.000. Given the result, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that exposure to violence has a significant influence on status delinquency among adolescents residing in Awka Metropolis. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis was accepted while the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two: Exposure to violence has no significant influence on property delinquent behaviour among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Exposure to Violence on Property Delinquent Behaviours among Adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Std. Mean	Error T	P-value
Exposure to violence has no significant influence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis	374	2.65	1.05	0.027	96.4	.000

Table 4 showed that the mean score of property delinquent behaviours was 2.65, standard deviation was 1.05, t value was 96.4, p value was 0.000. This indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected that exposure to violence has no influence on property delinquency among adolescents residing in Awka metropolis. Therefore, exposure to violence significantly influences property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka Metropolis.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The influence of exposure to violence on status delinquent behaviours among adolescents was analysed in table 1. The analysis showed that the responses on the various item statements were all greater than the critical mean level of 2.50 which indicated that there is a great effect of violence exposure on delinquent behaviour among adolescents. The effects include engaging in repeated physical fights, truancy, substance consumption, threatening others on social media and defying parental authority. The result is in line with the findings of Gupta, et al, (2022) who observed a strong relationship between cyberbullying and delinquency in adolescents. The finding also aligns with the result of Eweida et al, (2021). who found that cyberbullying experiences among Egyptian adolescents was associated with delinquent behaviours. Akyo et. al., (2024) found a significant correlation between exposure to violence and delinquency ($r = 154, p < .05$), demonstrating how witnessing family violence predicts misconducts. The findings also align with existing research Katembu et al, (2023), which reported that exposure to violence is linked to emotional desensitization, aggression, cognitive impairment, and antisocial tendencies. The findings align with Bronfenbrenner's ecological

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system theory on which the study is anchored which highlights the effects of interactions with the environment on the behaviour of an individual.

The analysis in table 2 revealed that there is a strong influence of exposure to violence on property delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis. The findings indicated that all the property-related behaviours apart from repeated stealing from classmates' lockers are associated with histories of witnessing violence directly or indirectly. In support of these findings, Akyo et. al., (2024) demonstrate that adolescents exposed to domestic violence often resort to stealing and property damage. Felix and Kayode (2023) study revealed that structural violence has a significant effect on property-related delinquency. Rosario et al (2003) also noted that community violence exposure increases the chances of property crimes among youths. In contrast, Umeh (2022) found no significant link between exposure to violence and vandalism. In addition, Lawal (2024) argued that moral upbringing among violence-exposed adolescents can buffer against delinquent outcomes. Lawal posited that family monitoring and peer support significantly mitigate the link between violence exposure and property delinquent behaviours.

However, the findings of the study were further tested in table 3 and table 4 using null hypothesis. The result of the null hypothesis revealed that exposure to violence significantly influence adolescents' delinquent behaviours. This finding coincides with the result of DiClemente and Richards (2022) who revealed that exposure to violence is linked to a series of behavioural and psychological problems. Allwood et al (2023) observed that exposure to violence has a significant effect on delinquent behaviours of adolescents. When teenagers are exposed to violence, their actions tend to gear towards deviant behaviours.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study were summarised as follows:

1. The study showed that exposure to violence influences status delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis to a high extent.
2. The study inferred that exposure to violence influences property delinquency among adolescents in Awka metropolis.

CONCLUSION

Delinquent behaviours among adolescents remains a significant social concern in contemporary society. Drawing on the findings of this study, it is therefore concluded that exposure to violence exerts a statistically significant influence on delinquent behaviours among adolescents in Awka metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, and the conclusions thereafter, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Counselling centers should be established to provide therapy and behavioural intervention programmes for adolescents exposed to violence, particularly those at risk of engaging in status offences.
2. Parents, care-givers and educators should guide teens on healthy media consumption and regulate exposure to violent content in movies, video games, and social media.

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